

IPCC Virtual Workspace at DKRZ

Short Url: http://bit.ly/IPCC_DKRZ_Virtual_Workspace

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1. Virtual Workspaces for IPCC AR6 Authors

Virtual Workspaces for IPCC authors provide support for the creation of figures. They were set up based on IPCC AR5 authors' experiences with ESGF, which led to a grey archive of a CMIP5 subset at ETH Zurich in support of AR5 authors.

Two Virtual Workspaces are available: JASMIN at CEDA and at DKRZ ([IPCC Virtual Workspaces](#)). They provide access to data pools and common climate software packages and enable the exchange of created figures with their underlying intermediate datasets and scripts among authors.

Virtual Workspaces are no data archives. Only limited storage is available.

2. Overview over Virtual Workspace at DKRZ

The Virtual Workspace for IPCC authors at DKRZ is part of DKRZ's High Performance Computer *Mistral*. IPCC authors get normal DKRZ user accounts for *Mistral*.

2.1 Who is DKRZ?

The mission of German Climate Computing Center ([DKRZ](#)) is to provide high performance computing (HPC) platforms, sophisticated and high capacity data management and services for premium climate science.

Beyond providing HPC services, DKRZ hosts the IPCC Data Distribution Centre ([IPCC DDC](#)) for climate model data and the World Data Center for Climate (WDCC), which is a Regular Member of the World Data System (WDS).

2.2 Numbers for Mistral

Mistral, the third HPC system for Earth system research (HLRE-3), is DKRZ's first petascale supercomputer. The HPC system has a peak performance of 3.14 PetaFLOPS and consists of approx. 3 300 compute nodes, 100 000 compute cores, 266 Terabytes of memory, and 54 Petabytes of disk (further information at: <https://www.dkrz.de/up/systems/mistral>).

3. New Users

3.1 User Registration

1. Register for a DKRZ user account: <https://luv.dkrz.de/projects/newuser/>
2. Apply to join project '**1088: DKRZ_MIP_Pool_Analysis**' (unix group: '**bk1088**):
 - Use link in the confirmation email to log into the user portal: <https://luv.dkrz.de>
 - Goto 'Project' and click on 'join existing project'
 - Select the project: '1088: DKRZ_MIP_Pool_Analysis' in the form
 - *Authors of Ch. 4 can select the project 'mh0482 (Data Store Admin MPI-M)' instead*

3.2 Getting Started

1. **Login (8 nodes):** `ssh [-X] <userid>@mistral.dkrz.de`
2. **Module Concept:** Common software packages are installed but have to be loaded:
 - Check packages loaded upon login: `module list`
 - List available packages: `module avail`
 - Load software package: `module load <package>`
3. **Storage:**
 - **HOME:** personal storage (24 GB): `/pf/b/<userid>`
 - **WORK:** shared project storage (50 TB): `/work/bk1088/<ch>`
 - **SCRATCH:** temporal storage (14 days): `/scratch/b/<userid>`

4. Best Practices

4.1 Data Storage

It is recommended to store personal scripts in HOME, shared scripts and shared small-scale datasets (e.g. intermediate datasets) in WORK and large temporal datasets in SCRATCH:

HOME: Private (test) scripts

WORK: Shared scripts and results - **structure your shared storage, e.g. by chapter!**

SCRATCH: Larger datasets for temporary storage and further analysis

4.2 Script Execution

- **Interactive:**
 - Small scripts can run directly on the login nodes;
 - Medium scripts should run on the post-processing nodes

```
ssh [-X] mistralpp
```
- **Batch (slurm - <https://www.dkrz.de/up/systems/mistral/running-jobs>):**
 - Large scripts have to run in batch mode. If you need to run batch jobs, please check the above documentation or contact data-pool@dkrz.de.
 - (Accounting! Available CPUs for project 'bk1088': 20 000 node hours)

5. Data and Software

Some data is available on disk, provided and owned by different projects (linux groups). Most of the data is on tape and accessible via the CERA interfaces.

5.1 Available Software

The list of installed software on Mistral is available at:

<https://www.dkrz.de/up/systems/mistral/softwarelist>

5.2 Available Data

The list of available data on disk and selected CERA data is collected in [IPCC: DKRZ Data Pool Content](#).

In case of CMIP6 data the [AR6 WG1 priority variables Public v1.0](#) are provided.

Two main entry points to data access are provided:

1. Disk: `/pool/data` (currently revised and extended)
2. Tape/CERA: <http://cera-www.dkrz.de> (see 5.4 for data access in scripts via jblob)

Further data on Mistral belongs to certain projects. Users need to request access to the project via the User Portal: <https://luv.dkrz.de>. For example, the observations underlying the ESMVal tool belong to the ESMVal project 'bd0854'.

5.3 Request for Additional Data in Data Pool

In case of data missing in DKRZ's data pool please send an email with the specification of the needed data to the following addresses:

1. CMIP6 Data:
 1. contact esgf-replication@dkrz.de
 2. enter data specification in the provided form
2. Other Data: contact data-pool@dkrz.de

5.4 CERA Data Access

Data is stored on tape but many frequently-accessed files are in the cache (on disk).

Use jblob in your scripts to access the data:

<https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/ceraresearch/info?site=jblob>

Jblob is installed on Mistral, please load it via:

```
module load jblob
```

5.5 Citation of Used Data

Please cite the used data in the text and add the data reference in the reference list. There are different possibilities to find data references, e.g. ESGF portal (<http://esgf-data.dkrz.de>), DataCite's search (<https://search.datacite.org>) or Google Dataset Search (<https://toolbox.google.com/datasetsearch>). Different possibilities to find data references are collected in in section 1 of the draft document in the resources folder of the IPCC Author Training workshop (06/2019):

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1HAIQyU02x5BrHz05HEu0v6iFiRBHZfPAYMsd349uiy0>

6. IPCC Specifics

6.1 Mistral:

- Synda tool for ESGF data replication (<http://prodiguer.github.io/synda/>):
module load synda
- Search for data in the data pool:
module load cmip6-dicad
freva --databrowser --help
- ESMVal tool support (further Information at: <https://cmip-esmvaltool.dkrz.de/>)

6.2 Web-based:

- ESGF Data Node: <http://esgf-data.dkrz.de>
- Jupyter Hub (python; further Information at:
<https://www.dkrz.de/up/systems/jupyterhub-dkrz.de-1/jupyterhub-dkrz.de>):
<http://jupyterhub.dkrz.de/>

References and Points of Contact

References

DKRZ User Portal (user account information):	https://luv.dkrz.de
Selected available Data in DKRZ Data Pool:	http://bit.ly/IPCC_DKRZ_Data
Available Software on Mistral:	https://www.dkrz.de/up/systems/mistral/softwarelist
CMIP6 project information:	https://pcmdi.llnl.gov/CMIP6/
AR6 WG1 Priority Variables:	https://goo.gl/tVaGko
CMIP6 data available in ESGF:	https://pcmdi.llnl.gov/CMIP6/ArchiveStatistics/esgf_data_holdings/
CMIP6 data references:	https://search.datacite.org/works?query=prefix:10.22033
CMIP6 Citation Service and Archival in DDC:	http://cmip6cite.wdc-climate.de
ESGF Data Portal:	http://esgf-data.dkrz.de
ESMVal for AR6 at DKRZ:	https://cmip-esmvaltool.dkrz.de/
IPCC WGI - DDC Data and Script Development Training (06/2019):	https://www.ipcc.ch/event/wgi-training-on-data-and-software-development/
Guidance on data references and provenance (draft):	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1HAIQyU02x5BrHz05HEu0v6lFiRBHZfPAYMsd349uiy0
IPCC Data Distribution Centre (IPCC DDC):	http://www.ipcc-data.org
IPCC DDC at DKRZ:	http://ipcc.wdc-climate.de
DKRZ:	http://www.dkrz.de

Points of Contact

Mistral and user account:

beratung@dkrz.de

Data and general questions:

data@dkrz.de

CMIP6 Data Pool:

data-pool@dkrz.de